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“REGRET ME NOT”

From the moment I laid eyes on you,
I never thought it might be true.
To behold a wonderful creation on earth,
Marvelous and exciting, you take my breath.

Approaching me with your tender touch,
Eyes filled with sensations that mean so much.
A feeling of ecstasy swells deep inside;
Who could forget? Who would preside?

Places and spaces in my world so few,
Only you have taken them into view.
Green trees whispering love so true,
An endless feeling of happiness and blue.

Was it your way to leave your heart?
Was it your plan from the very start?
In my most vulnerable state of mind,
Always remember when I leave—regret me not.